

"CONCERTMASTER SKILLS", ANALYSIS OF PEDAGOGICAL REPERTOIRE. (FEATURES OF THE ACCOMPANIMENT PART IN ROMANCES OF COMPOSERS OF UZBEKISTAN)

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Introduction:

The chamber and vocal creativity of composers in Uzbekistan is very diverse and multifaceted. It occupies an important place in the repertoire of modern performing musicians. In revealing the figurative structure of these works, the accompaniment part and its means of expression play a special role.

Accompaniment is a complex set of means of expression, among which one can note a harmonic basis, rhythmic pulsation, register and timbre coloring, texture features, musical imagery, etc. All these components represent a semantic unity that requires a special artistic performance solution.

The simplest form of harmonic support is to support a vocal melody with sustained chords on the main steps of the tonality. Such accompaniment is usually used for recitative constructions. Sometimes this type of texture is modified: its melodic "fullness" increases; the chords, although separated by pauses, are connected intonationally, acting as elements of a single melodic structure ("Bakhor" by T. Sadykov, "Chaman ichra" by S. Yudakov). The very components of such an accompaniment become more complex: a single chord turns into a group of chords due to repetition ("Yakkadir Toshkent" by D. Amanullayeva, "Four Lies" by S. Varelas).

The choral texture and its various modifications in the form of chord rehearsals dynamize the presentation due to the fragmentation of durations, ensuring the preservation of sufficient sound density at a slow tempo. Repeated chords (when using the damper pedal) convey a gradual increase in sound ("If the lips said "no"" by S. Varelas).

Of particular note is the duplication of the vocal part in the upper voice of a chord or octave accompaniment at certain stages of development (most often at climaxes). Such octave duplications give the melody a light, "airy" flavor, creating a feeling of spaciousness and freedom ("Zhonon Kurinur" by T. Sadykov, "Kushcha" by S. Yudakov, "Bakhor Kushigi" by M. Burkhanov).

The texture of the accompaniment often contains imitative, canonical polyphony (or its individual elements). Without resorting to the polyphonic form as a general means of constructing a romance, composers turn to it in connection with specific artistic tasks, freely interpreting the techniques of

polyphonic presentation and combining them with homophonic principles of structure.

The most frequently presented are imitations and canonical presentations that enhance the musical idea of the vocal part (“Chaman ichra” by S. Yudakov, “Bakhor kushigi” by M. Burkhanov, “If the lips said “no”” by S. Varelas).

A common type of texture is harmonic figuration in the form of arpeggios. Without losing its meaning as a harmonic basis, the arpeggiato chord acquires the quality of a temporary procedural extension. It distinguishes tempo, range, and dynamic amplitude. This type of texture comes from the expressive capabilities of string instruments and is characteristic of conveying lyrical feelings: thoughtfulness, tenderness, magic (“In the Fields...” by B. Gienko, “Night” by N. Narkhodzhaev, “Alla” by Z. Tuychieva).

Very often, the romances of Uzbek composers use dance rhythms and stylization of timbres similar to global dance forms (waltz, mazurka...) (“Carnival Waltz” by S. Yudakov, “Jenny” by B. Gienko, “Star Waltz” by A. Babaev); and under the forms of Uzbek dance folklore (ufar), in order to create a national flavor (“Dugonolar” by S. Yudakov, “Meni Islagim” by B. Umedjonov, “Song of Youth” by M. Ashrafi).

The sound representation of rhythmic movements with their subtle differentiation from the hesitant step of a person (“Er ketdi” by S. Babaev) to fast waltz movements (“Carnival Waltz” by S. Yudakov) becomes an exponent of a number of semantic shades.

In addition to texture, musical imagery plays an important role in the accompaniment of Uzbek romances. It occurs quite often in the vocal part, but its main carrier is the piano part. The figurativeness of the accompaniment part gives a vivid idea of the situation, the surrounding world, with which the hero’s experiences are connected; increases the specificity and completeness of the reflection of reality.

Figurativeness also includes a certain expressiveness, which contributes to the organic combination of vocal and piano parts: accuracy of reproduction is combined with a high degree of generalization. The accompanist must work to ensure that figurativeness does not interfere, but helps to reveal the main points of the romance’s content, without leading to excessive fragmentation of the composition, which reduces the unity and integrity of the artistic impact.

The types of expressiveness found in the accompaniment part are very diverse. A prominent place is occupied by the reproduction of birdsong (“Bul-bul” by T. Sadykov, “Bakhor kushigi” by M. Burkhanov); image of the water

element - from the silvery murmur of a brook to a mighty river flow (“Skullcap” by S. Varelas). There are often sound images of violent emotions: tears (“Greedy Boy” by S. Varelas), jubilation (“Song of Youth” by M. Ashrafi), etc. Often used is the reproduction of the sound of Uzbek folk instruments using a rhythmic and sound pattern typical for this instrument: chang (“Bakhor” by T. Sadykov), doira (“Chaman Ichra” by S. Yudakov), dutar (“Kuylama” by S. Yudakov), nay (“Bulbul” by T. Sadykov), gidzhak (“In the Fields” by B. Gienko). In some romances, not just one instrument is imitated, but a whole ensemble of instruments.

In the process of working on the accompaniment part, the accompanist must take into account all the above-mentioned features of the texture, paying attention to the sound of folk instruments and the dance rhythmic structure. All this will help create in an ensemble with a vocalist a full-fledged picture conceived by the composer; accurately convey the figurative content of the work and its semantic unity.

